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BRANCH IMPORT SUBSTITUTION STRATEGIES: INDICES OF THE EVALUATION OF THE EFFICIENCY OF IMPLEMENTATION

Abstract

The barely foreseeable multidirectionality together with the rapid rate of changes of environmental impacts, as well as the implementation of new and new sanction restrictions, negatively impact production activities of many enterprises of leading branches of Russian economics. In order to react against mentioned circumstances the Ministry of Industrial Development has worked out the complex of branch import replacement strategies, which to a great extent will be determined by the increasing efficiency of enterprises of leading branches of Russian economics. The article discloses the importance of the increasing efficiency of activities of enterprises of leading branches of Russian economics in terms of the negative impact of sanction restrictions, was also offered the system of resulting indices for its evaluation. The offered system is not an exhaustive one, anyway, many enterprises of leading branches of Russian economics, can use it for the evaluation of the efficiency of its activities.

Аннотация

Слабо предсказуемая разнонаправленность и стремительные изменения воздействий факторов внешней среды, а также введение все новых санкционных ограничений оказывают негативное влияние на производственную деятельность многих предприятий ведущих отраслей российской экономики. Для противодействия указанным обстоятельствам Министерством промышленного развития был разработан комплекс отраслевых стратегий импортозамещения, успешная реализация которых во многом будет определяться повышением эффективности деятельности предприятий ведущих отраслей российской экономики. В статье показана важность повышения эффективности деятельности предприятий ведущих отраслей российской экономики в условиях негативного влияния санкционных ограничений, а также предложена система результирующих показателей для ее оценки. Предложенная система не является исчерпывающей, однако многие предприятия ведущих отраслей российской экономики могут ее использовать для оценки эффективности своей деятельности.

Keywords: Russian economics, branch strategies, import substitution, efficiency evaluation.

Ключевые слова: российская экономика, отраслевые стратегии, импортозамещение, оценка эффективности.

Introduction

In different time many countries have used import substitution strategies for the development of the national economics. First of all, amongst it should be highlighted such countries as Brazil, Argentine, Mexico, as well as South Korea and Taiwan. In most of above mentioned countries, except Argentine, the development of import substitution strategies have promoted the growth of economics, as well as its diversification, the quick development of the industrialization, the reduced dependence from purchases of foreign technologies, items and completing parts, as well as the creation of new manufacturing and job sites. With that the successful implementation of import substitution strategies was followed by the export growth

and by the increase of the share of production with the high added value in its structure, what was becoming a good motivation for the implementation of innovations. With that basic instruments for the implementation of import substitution strategies and the motivation for the implementation of innovations were as such:

- use of protectionist measures for the motivation of the development of the national production at the expense of government allowances and the establishment of concessive prices for the in-house manufactured production for the motivation of the internal demand growth;
- establishment of different restrictions for purchases of foreign technologies, items and completing parts;
- upgrading of industrial enterprises of national economics at the expense of the investment of funds, gained from the implementation of import substitution strategies [1, p. 47].

As to Russian economics, issues, referred to the development and implementation of import substitution strategies, became of especially importance after the implementation of sanction restrictions, which have impacted the majority of leading branches of Russian economics. It has caused the considerable growth of prices, as well as have caused serious damage to the Russian consumer market and promoted the increasing capital outflow from the country. Anyway, even under most unfavorable conditions, sanction restrictions also have had positive influence on the development of certain industrial areas and of whole economics, becoming for it an effectual motivation for the implementation of import substitution strategies. The growth of prices and the reduction of purchases of imported goods, influenced by the devaluation of the real course of ruble, caused the increased demand for the Russian-made production, which started actively substituting foreign technologies, items and completing parts.

Research purpose

Provided varied peculiarities of the production organization at industrial enterprises of leading branches of Russian economics, as main purpose of this research was selected the consolidate approach to the evaluation of the efficiency of the implementation of branch import substitution strategies.

Materials and methods

The process of the implementation of the import substitution strategy represents the regulated complex of stages and actions, needed for the: situation analysis of the environment; goal setting for the branch development; working out of its development schedule; practical performance of the complex of certain events of such kind; control over the correspondence of scheduled and actual resulting indices [2, p. 24].

In order to determine the composition of resulting indices of the implementation of import substitution strategies in whole for Russian economics and its leading branches it is expedient to use the system of import dependent indices, which is formed on the basis of "Expenses-Release" tables and consolidates three groups of resulting indices. Some of resulting indices were used in the methodology and methods of the evaluation of the import dependence of Russian economics [3].

The first group comprises aggregated resulting indicators, characterizing the dependence of economics and of its leading branches from purchases of foreign made items, technologies and completing parts, determined by means of the direct count method. Several segments of leading economic branches interact at intermediate markets: intermediate production market (1), consumer market (2) and the market of the ready, including innovative production (3). These segments will be marked, accordingly, with K ($K=1, 2, 3$) indices. Among foreign-made items, technologies and completing parts we will highlight the intermediate imported production (IM) and final user imported production (IM_K). The later comprises the final user's imported production (IM_{Ei}) and the imported production, taken into account in the fixed gross capital formation (IM_{Ki}). Following forms can be used for the calculation of aggregated resulting indices

of the dependence of Russian economics and its leading branches from purchases of foreign made items, technologies and completing parts (1) - (4):

$$IZ_E = IM : (X + IM), \quad (1)$$

$$IZ_K = IM_K : (X_K + IM_K), \quad (2)$$

$$IZ_{Ei} = IM_{Ei} : (X_{Ei} + IM_{Ei}), \quad (3)$$

$$IZ_{Ki} = IM_{Ki} : (X_{Ki} + IM_{Ki}), \quad (4)$$

IZ_E and IZ_K are consolidated indices, characterizing the dependence of economics and of its leading branches from purchasing of foreign-made items, technologies and completing parts, IM is the volume of imported production, X – the volume of the manufactured national production, i – production kind index, $i=1, \dots, n$, where n is the number of kinds of production;

IZ_E – share of the total volume of purchases of foreign made items, technologies and completing parts, used in economics, resources of (national and imported) production, used in economics in total. Export-oriented resources are not excluded from the nominator, as for its manufacturing are used foreign made items, technologies and completing parts;

IZ_K – share of foreign made items, technologies and completing parts IM_K in the scope of production, used for the intermediate use of economics ($K=1$), for the final use of households ($K=2$) and the gross capital formation ($K=3$);

IZ_{Ei} and IZ_{Ki} – indices, characterizing the dependence of economics and of its leading branches from purchases of foreign made items, technologies and completing parts for i -type production;

IZ_{Ei} – share of the import of i (IM_i) kind in the i -kind production, used in economics;

IZ_{Ki} – share of used purchases of items, technologies and completing parts in the K field of i (IM_{iK}) kind in the scope of i kind of production, used in K field.

The second group comprises resulting indices, characterizing the dependence of Russian economics from purchases of foreign made items, technologies and completing parts at the level of branch industries. In order to evaluate the dependence of branch industries from purchases of foreign made items, technologies and completing parts are calculated two kinds of indices, with which is determined the share of purchases of foreign made items, technologies and completing parts in the scope, used at the production manufacturing (formulas (5) - (6)), and the import consumption of the branch release ((7) - (8)).

The share of purchases of foreign made items, technologies and completing parts in the i kind of production, used in the intermediate consumption of the j area is calculated by the formula:

$$IZ_{ij} = IM_{ij} : (X_{ij} + IM_{ij}). \quad (5)$$

The share of purchases of foreign-made items, technologies and completing parts in the whole intermediate consumption for the j area is determined by the formula:

$$IZ_{pp_{ij}} = \Sigma IM_{ij} : \Sigma (X_{ij} + IM_{ij}). \quad (6)$$

The import consumption of the release of the j area for the i kind of production is determined by the formula:

$$im_{ij} = IM_{ij} : X_{ij}. \quad (7)$$

The import consumption of the whole release for the j area is determined by the formula:

$$im_{x_j} = \Sigma IM_{ij} : X_j. \quad (8)$$

In formulas (5) - (8) $j=1, \dots, m$, where m is the number of branches.

The third group comprises the resulting index for the determination of complete expenses for the purchase of foreign-made items, technologies and completing parts in the cost of the final national production. In order to determine complete expenses for the purchase of the national production in the total volume of the cost of the final national production and to obtain the summary volume of the national production in the final consumption, gross accumulation and the export component the (9) formula is used. Its numerator represents the scope of expenses for the purchase of the intermediate imported production (consumed in branch productions):

$$IZ_{KIO} = IM_{pp} : (KP + VN + EX). \quad (9)$$

As the Russian economics functions in terms of sanction restrictions for more than 5 years, it seems expedient to substantiate the system of indices for the evaluation of the efficiency of the implementation of import substitution strategies in some branches of Russian economics. Anyway, before the substantiation of the composition of such system indices, let's highlight that the development and the implementation of branch import substitution strategies became the countermeasure for the protection of Russian economics from uncompetitive methods, aimed to hinder its development and for the support of the competitive ability of the Russian-made production [4, p. 304]. The main result of the implementation of import substitution strategies at the level of several branches and enterprises is to reduce its dependence from purchases of foreign technologies, items and completing parts and to provide for the growth of national economics at the expense of internal resources. In favorable conditions these processes can be accompanied by the increase of the export share of the national production at world markets.

As a first the system of indices for the evaluation of the efficiency of the implementation of import substitution strategies in sectors (branches) of Russian economics, following indices should be included:

- scope of production for (*i*) kinds, released only with the use of own made items and completing parts (*CP*) V_{CPit} with actual and cost measurement for a certain time period (10);
- scope of production for (*i*) kinds, released only with use of own and foreign made items and completing parts (*ICP*) V_{ICPit} with actual and cost measurement for a certain time period (11);

- total volume of the production release by V_{PRit} kinds for a certain time period, which is determined by the formula:

$$V_{PRit} = V_{CPit} + V_{ICPit} \quad (12)$$

- coefficient of use of own made items and completing parts (k_{CIIit}) in the total volume of the production release by V_{PRit} kinds for a certain time period, which is determined by the formula:

$$k_{CPIit} = \frac{V_{CPIit}}{V_{PRit}} \times 100\%. \quad (13)$$

- coefficient of use of own and foreign made items and completing parts (k_{ICPit}) in the total volume of the production release by V_{PRit} kinds for a certain time period, which is determined by the formula:

$$k_{ICPit} = \frac{V_{ICPit}}{V_{PRit}} \times 100\%. \quad (14)$$

- coefficient of the import dependence of the total volume of production release by kinds ($k_{V_{CPit}}$) for a certain time period, which is determined by the formula:

$$k_{V_{CPit}} = \frac{V_{CPit}}{V_{ICPit}} \times 100\%. \quad (15)$$

- index of the provision of the total volume of the production release for all V_{CPit} kinds for a certain time period by own made items and completing parts (Δk_{Oit}), which is determined by the formula:

$$\Delta k_{Oit} = k_{CPIit} - k_{ICPit}. \quad (16)$$

Results and discussion

For the purpose of the complete evaluation of the share of expenses for the purchase of the imported production in the cost of different kinds of national production, oriented to the final consumption, accumulation and export are used more complicated calculation formulas in

comparison with given ones (1-9). It is based on the accounting of ratios of the full import consumption of different kinds of national-made final production.

The increase of values of 10, 12, 13, 15 and 16 indices with the simultaneous decrease of 11 and 14 indices will witness the increasing efficiency of the implementation of import substitution strategies both for branches of Russian economics, as well as at certain industrial enterprises.

The given approach to the substantiation of the system of indices for the evaluation of the efficiency of the implementation of branch import substitution strategies is applied for only such kinds of production, for which state statistics disposes the comparative data in the context of the use at its production of both own and foreign-made items and completing parts.

Conclusion

On the basis of results, obtained in the course of studies, following opinions can be made:

1. Enterprises of leading branches of Russian economics not only oppose to sanction restrictions, but also continue its successful development. In terms of strict competition at international markets it managed to increase volumes of gross product manufacturing, so providing for the successful implementation of import substitution strategies.

2. Was offered the system of resulting indices, which can be applied for the evaluation of the efficiency of activities of most enterprises of leading branches of Russian economics, as well as for the evaluation of the implementation by them of branch import substitution strategies. This system is not exhaustive and needs the following workout in the context of the awareness of production peculiarities and of the certain nomenclature of the gross production in certain branches of Russian economics.

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